

A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF SUBSURFACE LAYER IN DETERMINATION OF POTENTIAL AQUIFERS IN LAGOS METROPOLIS AND ITS ENVIRONMENT

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Abstract: A geophysical survey employing vertical electrical sounding (VES) was carried out within Lagos metropolis, which spread across Ikorodu, Abule Egba, Ikeja, Ayobo, and the Magboro axis, using a Schlumberger electrode configuration with half-current electrode separation (AB/2) varying from 1 to 100 m with the aid of a resistivity instrument (an Ohm mega resistivity meter). The aim is to delineate the temporal strata encountered in each location to determine a possible lateral correlation among the aquifers in the study areas. A total of six (6) VES points were mapped, and the computed apparent resistivity data (Ωm) obtained at each station was plotted against the half-current electrode separation (AB/2). The resulting resistivity curves were then interpreted using Winresist software. The thrust of this study is to determine the subsurface layer and hydrogeological parameters of a potential aquifer for groundwater exploration for the local communities. The geoelectric section generated from the results of the VES revealed topsoil, laterite, sand, sandstone, limestone, clay, and shale of varying thicknesses, suggesting variation in the layering of the strata, which makes their correlation not practicable. A close geophysical investigation should be done in Lagos metropolis as an interpolation. The VES results show that good potential aquifers were recorded in the Ayobo, Magboro, and Ikorodu areas, which makes them good aquifers. This will serve as a guide in the construction and drilling of boreholes in the study areas.

Keyword: Geophysical survey, Vertical electrical sounding, Subsurface layer, Lagos metropolis

I. INTRODUCTION

Groundwater occurs in varied quantities in almost all rock formations. But to meet the requirement in any one place, it must occur in substantial quantity. There are several factors that control the distribution, quality, quantity, and circulation of groundwater. These factors include geological factors such as the lithology, textural characteristics, and structures of the rock. The quantity and deposition of groundwater depend on the geological characteristics of the host rock [8,9]. Groundwater may occur on a large scale within an aquifer of varying thickness stretching over long distances, but the quality and deposition may not.

One of the methods of exploration commonly used for groundwater is the electrical resistivity method to study the horizontal and vertical discontinuities using the electrical properties of the rock at the subsurface. It is also useful in delineating extensive aquifers constituting horizontally stratified earth with a varied depth of penetration. The method is targeted at investigating the shallow subsurface geology of the area [1,9]. Due to the electrical properties of the earth masses, the electrical resistivity of different geological materials is a function of several factors, which include variations in water contents, dissolved ions in water, and material make-up. Resistivity investigations can thus be used to identify zones with different electrical properties [2,3]. This paper aims to generate baseline information that can be interpolated in part of Lagos metropolis generally, which will help to develop an understanding of the key properties of the subsurface horizontal strata in the study area with the aim of determining the geoelectric characteristics of five locations in Lagos, delineating each of the layers encountered based on variations in their electrical properties, identifying the aquifer units, and evaluating the groundwater potential of the survey area.

II. THE STUDY AREA

Lagos metropolis falls between the Lagos mainland and the Atlantic Ocean [9]. The study area is on the southwestern coast of Nigeria, approximately between latitudes $6^{\circ}22'N$ and $6^{\circ}52'N$ and longitudes $2^{\circ}42'E$ and $3^{\circ}42'E$ [11]. The area is bounded on the west by the Republic of Benin, while the southern boundary of the state is formed by the 180km-long Atlantic coastline (Figures 1 and 2). Its northern and eastern boundaries are shared with Ogun State [11]. The landmark area of the study area is 3,577 km², about 22 percent of which is water [13]. Metropolitan Lagos constitutes about 33% of Lagos State, with 455 sq. km of the metropolis being water bodies, wetlands, and mangrove swamps [16]. The study area was carried out in the following location (Fig. 1).

1. Ayobo: $6^{\circ}36'04.66''N$ and $3^{\circ}14'33.70''E$
2. Magboro: $6^{\circ}42'15.42''N$ and $3^{\circ}24'11.59''E$
3. Ikorodu: $6^{\circ}34'56.84''N$ and $3^{\circ}31'32.22''E$
4. Abule Egba: $6^{\circ}38'53.79''N$ and $3^{\circ}17'57.25''E$
5. Ikeja: $6^{\circ}36'07.60''N$ and $3^{\circ}22'25.90''E$

Figure 1: Location map of the study area showing the VES point

Figure 2: Geological map of Lagos

2.1. Geologic Setting of Dahomey Basin

The Dahomey Basin is an inland, coastal, or offshore basin that runs from southern Ghana through Togo and the Republic of Benin to southwestern Nigeria. It is separated from the Niger Delta by a subsurface basement ridge known as the Okitipupa Ridge. Its offshore boundaries are not well defined. Sediment deposition moves east-west [4,5]. The Upper Cretaceous (mainly Maestichtian) rocks at the outcrop and along the present-day beach are mostly sandy and were most likely deposited during the first post-Santonian sedimentary cycle [10]. Cretaceous layers onshore are approximately 200 m thick [14,15]. The Akinbo shale is the oldest Cenozoic formation exposed in the Nigerian region of the Dahomey Basin, whereas the Benin formation and alluvial deposits are the newest. The Cenozoic formations that appear in the Nigerian region of the Dahomey include the Akinbo Shale, Ewekoro Formation, Oshoshun Formation, Ilaro Formation, and alluvium Coastal Plain Sands (Fig. 3). The Cenozoic formations are poorly exposed and difficult to map due to dense tropical vegetation and superficial deposits.

AGE		GROUP	FORMATIONS
QUATERNARY			
TERTIARY	PLIOCENE		
	MIOCENE		ILARO
	OLIGOCENE		OSOSUN
	EOCENE		AKINBO
	PALEOCENE		EWEKORO
CRETACEOUS	MAASTRICHTIAN		ARAROMI
	CAMPANIAN		
	SANTONIAN		
	CONIACIAN		AFOWO
	TURONIAN		
	CENOMANIAN		
	ALBIAN		
	APTIAN		
	BARREMIAN		
	NEOCOMIAN		
			ISE OKITIPIIPA RIDGE (BASEMENT)

Figure 3: Stratigraphic setting of Dahomey basin

III. METHODOLOGY

Vertical electrical sounding (VES) is used to investigate resistivity variation with depth. In this method, the distance between current electrodes from the probing point is varied equally, and the distance corresponds to the depth to which current is passed. In vertical electrical sounding, you have the same traverse but are interested in a particular point. The depth will not be constant but will vary. The basis for creating an electrical sound, regardless of the electrode array employed, is the idea that the deeper the depth of inquiry, the further the potential measurement is from the current source (Fig. 4). At the same center point, successive apparent resistivity values are calculated for increasing electrode spacing values [7,17]. A plot of the apparent resistivity values as a function of electrode spacing is made on bi-logarithmic paper to obtain a sounding curve. Schlumberger arrays are most applicable for electrical drilling. In this arrangement, it is required that the distance between the potential electrodes, M and N, never exceed one-fifth of half the spacing of the current electrodes, A and B, that is, $MN \leq AB/10$, and the ratio between two adjacent current electrode separations should be about 1 to 1.5 [6]. In vertical electrical sounding (VES), the potential electrodes remain fixed while the current electrode spacing is expanded symmetrically about the center of the spread. When the distance between the current electrodes exceeds the distance between the potential electrodes, the potential electrodes must be pushed outwards, or the potential difference

will be too tiny to measure accurately. At this point, a new number for potential-electrode spacing, x , is chosen, which is generally 2 to 4 times greater than the previous value, and the survey continues.

Figure 4: Configuration and Set-up of Schlumberger Resistivity Survey method

IV. RESULTS

Vertical Electrical Sounding (VES) methods are best for the detection of this anomaly. A resistivity instrument (a resistivity meter) was used for the survey using a Schlumberger electrode configuration with half-current electrode separation ($AB/2$) varying from 1 to 100 m. A total of one (5) VES points at different localities in Lagos State were mapped, and the computed apparent resistivity data (Ωm) obtained at each station was plotted against the half-current electrode separation ($AB/2$).

4.1 Resistivity sounding result.

From the resistivity sounding curve carried out in each of the locations. The resistivity sounding curves generated are of the H, KH, K, A, and HK curve types (Fig. 5). The predominant curve type in the study area is the H type. The number of geoelectric layers varies between 4 and 5 layers. The layers were typical of a succession of relatively low- and high-resistivity layers.

Table 2: Layer Parameters and VES curve types

VES NO	RESISTIVITIES (Ωm)	THICKNESS (m)	CURVE TYPE
1	1079/304/2424/1884/162	2.9/4.5/6.4/11.7/ α	HK
2	240/457/669/543/284	0.6/13.3/9.9/14.4/ α	K
3	34/89/2/33/437	2.6/2.2/7.0/7.0/ α	KH
4	36/104/461/582/442	0.9/9.4/7.4/16.7/ α	A
5	103/78/410/160	2.1/3.8 /5.9/42.2/ α	H
6	33/3/7/42/132	2.8/4.9/4.1/7.2/ α	H

Figure 5: VES diagram of different locations in Lagos.

4.2 Geoelectric section

The geoelectric sections enabled the identification of the various lithological units within the study area. The geoelectric sections are 2-dimensional imaging of the subsurface based on the geoelectric parameters (resistivity and depth) obtained from the inversion of the electrical resistivity sounding data.

Geoelectric section of VES 1: Five geoelectric layers were delineated along this geoelectric section. The resistivity value of the first layer is 1079 Ωm , and the thickness value is 2.9 m. The second layer resistivity is 304 Ωm , while the thickness is 4.5 m. The third layer has a resistivity value of 2424 Ωm and a thickness of 6.4 m, while the fourth and fifth layers have 1884 Ωm , 162 Ωm , and 11.7 m, respectively.

Geoelectric section of VES 2: Five geoelectric layers were delineated along this geoelectric section. The resistivity value of the first layer is 240 Ωm , and the thickness value is 0.6m. The second layer has a 475 Ωm resistivity and a thickness of 13.3m. The third layer has a resistivity of 669 Ωm and a thickness of 9.9m. The fourth layer has a resistivity value of 543 Ωm and a thickness of 14.4m, while the fifth layer has a resistivity value of 248 Ωm and a thickness of α .

Geoelectric section of VES 3: A total of five geoelectric layers were delineated along this study. The resistivity value of the first layer is 34 Ωm , and the thickness value is 2.6m. The second layer has 89 Ωm resistivity and a thickness of 2.2m. The third layer has a resistivity value of 2.4 Ωm and a thickness of 7m. The fourth layer has a resistivity value of 33 Ωm with a 7 m thickness, whereas the fifth layer has a resistivity value of a resistivity value of 437 Ωm and α , respectively.

Geoelectric section of VES 4: Across this study, a total of five geoelectric sections were delineated. The resistivity value of the first layer is $36\Omega\text{m}$, and the thickness value is 0.9m . The second layer has a 104m resistivity and a thickness of 9.4m . The third layer has a resistivity value of 461m and a thickness of 7.4m . The fourth and fifth layers have a resistivity value of $582\Omega\text{m}$, $442\Omega\text{m}$, 16.7m , and infinite thickness, respectively.

Geoelectric section of VES 5: A total of four geoelectric layers were delineated along this study. The resistivity value of the top layer is $103\Omega\text{m}$, and the thickness value is 2.1m . The second layer has a $78\Omega\text{m}$ resistivity and a thickness of 3.8m . The third layer has a resistivity value of $410\Omega\text{m}$ with a thickness of 5.9m , while the fourth layer has a resistivity value of a resistivity value of $160\Omega\text{m}$ and an infinite thickness.

Geoelectric section of VES 6: Across this study, a total of five geoelectric sections were delineated. The resistivity value of the top layer is 33m , and the thickness value is 2.8m . The second layer has a $3\Omega\text{m}$ resistivity and a thickness of 4.9m . The third layer has a resistivity value of $7\Omega\text{m}$ and a thickness of 4.1m . The fourth layer has a resistivity value of $42\Omega\text{m}$ with a thickness of a thickness of 7.2m , whereas the fifth layer has a resistivity value of $132\Omega\text{m}$ with an infinite thickness.

V. DISCUSSION

The study was carried out in Lagos Metropolis. The study showed the subsurface lithology and geologic sequence in Ayobo, Ikeja, Ikorodu, Abule Egba, and Magboro. The subsurface layers were delineated using vertical electrical sounding (VES). A total of six (6) VES points was carried out. Based on this geophysical investigation, we were able to deduce that the study area is composed of laterite, clay, sand, shale, and limestone. In each locality, the aquifer units were delineated as occurring at different depths and thicknesses.

Two VES points were carried out in the Ikorodu area. The VES-1 consists of laterite, shale, sandstone, and limestone. The aquifer unit in the area is sandstone, with a resistivity of $1884\Omega\text{m}$ and 11.7m thickness. The sandstone has good aquifer potential, and the type of aquifer in this study area is confined. The VES-2 Point also consists of laterite, shale, sandstone, and limestone. The aquifer unit in the area is sandstone, with a resistivity of $543\Omega\text{m}$ and 14.4m thickness. This indicates that the VES-1 has more potential groundwater for exploration than the VES-2 in the Ikorodu vicinity.

VES-3 points were carried out by Abule Egba. The area consists of laterite, sand, clay, and sandstone. The aquifer unit in the area is sandstone, with a resistivity of $33\Omega\text{m}$ and 7m thickness characteristic of the coastal plain sands. The sandstone has good aquifer potential for groundwater, and the type of aquifer in this study area is confined. In the Ikeja area, a VES-4 point was carried out. The layers in this area include topsoil, sand, laterite, sand, and clay. The aquifer unit in the area is sand, with a resistivity of $582\Omega\text{m}$ and a 16.7m thickness characteristic of coastal plain sands. The sand is considered to have poor aquifer potential.

A single VES-5 point was also carried out in the Ayobo area, delineating four layers, which include laterite, sand, clay, and sandstone. The layers in this area include laterite, sand, clay, and sandstone. The aquifer unit in the area is sand, which has excellent aquifer potential for groundwater exploration with a resistivity of $410\Omega\text{m}$ and a 42.2m thickness. The sandstone has good aquifer potential, and the type of aquifer in this study area is confined. VES 6 points were carried out by Magboro. The area consists of laterite, sand, clay, and sandstone. The aquifer unit in the area is sandstone, with a resistivity of $42\Omega\text{m}$ and a 7.2m thickness characteristic of the coastal plain sands. The sandstone has good aquifer potential, and the type of aquifer in this study area is confined.

VI. CONCLUSION

The geoelectric section generated from the VES results of the study areas revealed different lithologies, which include topsoil, laterite, sand, sandstone, limestone, clay, and shale of varying thicknesses, suggesting variation in the layering of the strata, which makes their correlation not practicable. Out of the number of VES carried out in the study area, only VES 2 and 4 are poor aquifers for groundwater exploration. VES 1 and 3 are good potential aquifers for groundwater, whereas VES 5 and 6 are excellent potential aquifers for groundwater exploration. This can serve as a guide in the construction and drilling of boreholes in the area.

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